

The Roots of Western Society's Architecture

We have observed that authenticity is a concept born from a person's response to their environment and a history of interaction that continues to shape their future with it. From this point, our focus shifts to how both the Western and Arab concepts influence the formation of their societies, how individuals perceive themselves within their communities, and what societal structures look like in each case. I will begin with modern Western society because it represents our current lived reality and is the most dominant and influential globally.

Starting from the modern Western concept of the environment—as discussed in the previous article—which views nature through an external lens that judges and categorizes it alongside living and non-living beings, we unconsciously adopt several assumptions:

1. That humans are on the same level as materials and other living or non-living entities.
2. That science is a perspective separate from both the environment and humanity, one that rises above to judge and exert authority.

3. That the default state of all beings is to be known by science, unless proven otherwise—either through scientific methodology or by a theory's failure to match observed reality, prompting reevaluation and reclassification.

The reason behind this social structure—where a superior perspective theorizes people's lives and decides what is best for them—can be traced back to the pre-modern era. Max Weber, in *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*, links the hierarchical church structure of pre-modern Europe with its continuation into the post-modern era. In other words, Western society, reacting to the church's resistance to scientific truths, replaced papal authority with scientists at the top of the hierarchy, while maintaining the same church-like structure. Herein lies the problem:

By sanctifying science, we have essentially sanctified scientists—just as the Catholic Church sanctified God through the infallibility of the Pope. But scientists are human; they make mistakes. The second point is that the church claimed exclusive ownership of truth through divine revelation—a revelation that spoke not only to what *is*, but also to what *will be*, being timeless and consistent with the nature of the universe.

Science, by contrast, is limited to what scientists have managed to perceive and prove. Its predictions of the future are merely hypotheses—extrapolations based on acquired data.

The third and most important point: in the church's structure, theological truth was to be constantly disseminated from the top down, and an individual would ascend socially by embracing and applying these divine teachings.

When this same structure is applied to science, the individual becomes an empty vessel of no value until filled by institutions—educational and media—with scientific facts. People become categorized as “modern” or “non-modern,” “believer” or “infidel,” depending on whether they adhere to this system—paralleling the papal concepts of faith and heresy.

Western society indeed succeeded in liberating itself from the tyranny of the corrupt papal institution and improved its quality of life, extending luxury once reserved for the ecclesiastical elite (as seen in Tivoli and Rome) to the broader population through science. But in doing so, it failed to see that it had maintained the same structure, only transferring the oppressive power from its own society to the unknown world—whether in dealing with nature or with foreign communities.

Modernity sees those outside its system as raw, untapped natural resources—not fully human, unqualified to govern themselves. This was illustrated by Edward Said in *Culture and Imperialism*, where he explains how modernity used literature to describe the non-Western world as waiting to be discovered, its treasures unearthed, and its people rescued from savagery. One example was how Africans were placed in cages in zoos, displayed like newly discovered species of apes from African jungles.

Thus, we see the core problem of modernity is not the sanctification of science—because science is indeed a noble and sacred pursuit—nor was the problem originally with Christianity itself, but with its moral corruption. By replacing the Pope with scientists and retaining the same structure, while neglecting spiritual and ethical dimensions, modern Western society has become dominated by material rationalism, where utility and power override all else.

When we examine architecture through this historical lens of Western societal roots, we see a continuation of how the church once used art and architecture to consolidate power—turning artists into directors and filmmakers, envisioning how science might deliver us to a refined, futuristic life. Architects became the translators of science's vision of the world.

Rather than being confined to the church, art and architecture now shape collective public space, reinforcing faith in a scientific future. Cities have become arenas of visual competition for attention

—battlegrounds for aesthetic dominance through any means available: height (as in skyscrapers), beauty (as in the works of Frank Gehry), futuristic fantasy (as in Rem Koolhaas's Star Wars-inspired designs), or techno-architecture that exposes the building as a visible machine (like the Centre Pompidou in Paris).

In all these forms, the human is reduced to a funder and space-filler, with architecture serving to express science's capacity to build a better future. Yet this vision of luxury quickly collided with reality — via climate change and ozone depletion.

Maintaining this worldview has transformed science into a new religion, and the architect into a maker of idols.

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